

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 21:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 21:1 לְמִנְצַחַת מִזְמוֹר</p>
<p>Psa. 21:1 O LORD, in Your strength the King will ^abe glad,</p>	<p>לְדָוִד : 2 יְהוָה בְּעֹזֶךָ יִשְׂמַח- מֶלֶךְ וּבִישׁוּעָתֶךָ מֵהַיְגִיל</p>
<p>And in Your ¹salvation how greatly he will rejoice!</p>	<p>[יְגַל] מְאֹד : 3 תַּאֲנוּת לְבוֹ</p>
<p>² You have ^agiven him his heart's desire,</p>	<p>נָתַתָּה לוֹ וְאַרְשֵׁת שְׂפָתָיו</p>
<p>And You have not withheld the request of his lips. ¹Selah.</p>	<p>בְּלֹ-מִנְעַת סֵלָה : 4 כִּי-</p>
<p>³ For You ^ameet him with the blessings of good things;</p>	<p>תִּקְדָּמְנוּ בְּרִכּוֹת טוֹב תְּשִׁית</p>
<p>You set a ^bcrown of fine gold on his head.</p>	<p>לְרֹאשׁוֹ עֲטֹרַת פָּז : 5 תַּיִם </p>
<p>⁴ He asked life of You, You ^agave it to him,</p>	<p>שָׁאַל מִמֶּךָ נָתַתָּה לוֹ אֲרָךְ</p>
<p>⁵ His ^aglory is great through Your ¹salvation,</p>	<p>יָמִים עוֹלָם וְעַד : 6 גְּדוֹל</p>
<p>^bSplendor and majesty You place upon him.</p>	<p>כְּבוֹדוֹ בִישׁוּעָתֶךָ הוֹד וְהָדָר</p>
<p>⁶ For You make him ¹most ^ablessed forever;</p>	<p>תְּשִׁינָה עָלָיו : 7 כִּי-תִשִׁיתָהוּ</p>
<p>You make him joyful ^bwith gladness in Your presence.</p>	<p>בְּרִכּוֹת לְעַד תִּתְהַדְּהוּ</p>
<p>Psa. 21:7 For the King ^atrusts in the LORD,</p>	<p>בְּשִׂמְחָה אֶת-פָּנָיֶךָ : 8 כִּי-</p>
<p>And through the lovingkindness of the Most High ^bhe will not be shaken.</p>	<p>הַמֶּלֶךְ בְּטִיחַ בֵּיתוֹה וּבִתְסֹד</p>
<p>⁸ Your hand will ^afind out all your enemies;</p>	<p>עֲלִיזוֹן בְּלֹ-יָמוּט : 9 תִּמְצָא</p>
<p>Your right hand will find out those who hate you.</p>	<p>יָדֶךָ לְכָל-אֹיְבֶיךָ יִמְיָנֶךָ</p>
<p>⁹ You will make them ^aas a fiery oven in the time ¹of your anger;</p>	<p>תִּמְצָא שְׂנְאֵיֶךָ : 10 תִּשִׁיתָמוּ </p>
	<p>כְּתַנּוּר אֵשׁ לְעֵת פָּנֶיךָ יְהוָה</p>
	<p>בְּאִפּוֹ יִבְלָעֵם וְתֹאכְלֵם אֵשׁ :</p>
	<p>11 פְּרִימוֹ מֵאַרְץ הַתְּאֵבֵד</p>

The LORD will ^bswallow them up
in His wrath,

And ^cfire will devour them.

¹⁰ Their ¹offspring You will destroy
from the earth,

And their ^{2a}descendants from
among the sons of men.

¹¹ Though they ^{1a}intended evil
against You

And ^bdevised a plot,

They will not succeed.

¹² For You will ^amake them turn their
back;

You will ¹aim ^bwith Your
bowstrings at their faces.

¹³ Be exalted, O LORD, in Your
strength;

We will ^asing and praise Your
power.

וְזָרְעָם מִבְּנֵי אָדָם : ¹² כִּי־נִטְוּ
עָלֵיךָ רָעָה חֲשָׁבוּ מִזְמָה

בְּלִי־יִוָּכְלוּ : ¹³ כִּי תִשְׁתַּמּוּ

שָׁכֶם בְּמִיתְרֵיךָ תִּכּוּנֵן עַל־

פְּנֵיהֶם : ¹⁴ רִוַּמָּה יִהְיֶה בְּעֵינֶיךָ

נִשְׁיָרָה וְנִזְמָרָה גְבוּרָתְךָ :

References

<p>Psalm 21:3 ^aPs 59:10 ^b2 Sam 12:30</p> <p>Psalm 21:4 ^aPs 61:6; 133:3 ^bPs 91:16</p> <p>Psalm 21:5 ¹Or <i>victory</i> ^aPs 9:14; 20:5 ^bPs 8:5; 96:6</p> <p>Psalm 21:6 ¹Lit <i>blessings</i> ^a1 Chr 17:27 ^bPs 43:4</p> <p>Psalm 21:7 ^aPs 125:1 ^bPs 112:6</p> <p>Psalm 21:8 ^aIs 10:10</p> <p>Psalm 21:9 ¹Or <i>of your presence</i> ^aMal 4:1 ^bLam 2:2 ^cPs 50:3</p> <p>Psalm 21:10 ¹Lit <i>fruit</i> ²Lit <i>seed</i> ^aPs 37:28</p>	<p>Psalm 21:11 ¹Lit <i>stretched out</i> ^aPs 2:1-3 ^bPs 10:2</p> <p>Psalm 21:12 ¹Lit <i>make ready</i> ^aPs 18:40 ^bPs 7:12, 13</p> <p>Psalm 21:13 ^aPs 59:16; 81:1</p>
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Targum

Psa. 21:1 For praise; a psalm of David. ² O LORD, in your strength the King Messiah will rejoice, and how greatly will he exult in your redemption! ³ You have given him the desire of his soul; and you have not withheld the expression of his lips forever. ⁴ For you will make good blessings go before him; you will place on his head a crown of refined gold. ⁵ Eternal life he asked of you; you gave him length of days forever and ever. ⁶ Great is his glory in your redemption; praise and splendor you will place on him. ⁷ Because you will give him blessings forever; you will gladden him with the gladness that is from your presence. ⁸ Because the King Messiah hopes in the LORD; and through the favor of the Most High he is not shaken. ⁹ The blow of your hand will reach all your foes; the vengeance of your right hand will find all your enemies. ¹⁰ You will make them like a fiery furnace at the time of your anger, O LORD; in his anger he will swallow them up and the inferno of Gehenna will consume them. ¹¹ You will make their children perish from the earth, and their progeny from the sons of men. ¹² Because they plotted evil against you, they thought evil thoughts, but they could not prevail against you. ¹³ Because for your people you made them one porter in the ropes of your tabernacle; you will prepare their way before them. ¹⁴ Stand up, O LORD, in your might; let us sing praise and dance in your strength.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

This Psalm is dedicated to David and the Messiah. Each suffers from enemies who want to deny them their sovereignty. David was taunted by those who rebelled after his affair with Bathsheba. The Messiah will suffer at the hands of Gog and Magog. The Messiah will have wisdom greater than King Solomon and teach the nation and guide them back to the LORD.

Superscript

לְמִנְצֵחַ (lam'nazecha) – the English translations of this Psalm like to use the phrase “for the choir director,” however this translation is inaccurate. The “Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament” indicates that this translation is far from correct. A proper translation is “To Netzach.” The Sefirah Netzach offers victory when its light is placed upon a person. The implication is that the people are happy that David had so many military victories. When David was victorious, the people were protected and prospered. The people are offering this prayer about David and their allegiance to him and the Sefirot Netzach.

To the Sefirot Netzach, a psalm of David.

Verse One

בְּעִזָּתְךָ (b'az'cha) – “in Your strength.” This word also signified that David could withstand any attack. He had the strength of the LORD with him. At crucial moments

in his life, the LORD gave him **יְשׁוּעָה** (y^eshu^á) salvation. With the LORD at his side, David rejoiced, knowing that the Sefirot Netzach was with him. The Christian church holds this Psalm as a messianic prophecy because the name of the Messiah is in the verse.

O LORD, in your strength, the King rejoices, and from your salvation, the power of Netzach he exults.

Verse Two

The LORD gave David everything that he yearned for in his heart.

You have given him everything that he yearned for and gave him what his lips spoke. Meditate on this verse.

Verse Three

The LORD willed David to be the King of Israel. David was given the finest of blessings of good fortune.

You made him the King of Israel and gave him good fortune.

Verse Four

David asked the LORD for a life to be charged with a part of the divine plan. He sought to do the work of the LORD. It was a calling that went beyond his existence. David also asked for a calling that reached far beyond his own life. He asked for the LORD's plan to include his descendants.

He asked for life, and you gave it to him; a length of days and a future destiny.

Verse Five

Through the salvation of the LORD, David was able to win battles against the LORD's enemies and thus increased his honor and majesty. David called upon the Sefirah Hod for the LORD's splendor and majesty through his victories on the battlefield.

The Sefirot Hod bestowed splendor and majesty upon him through Your salvation.

Verse Six

David's Psalms have become a spiritual blessing to the people of the world. The Psalms are a part of the promise that the LORD gave to Abraham that the people of the world would be blessed through him.

For You appointed him for blessings for the distant future; You made him shine with gladness in the LORD's sovereignty.

Verse Seven

David acknowledges that his faith in the LORD is a part of the fulfillment of his being the King.

The King trusts in the LORD, and because of the blessings from the Sefirah Chesed, he will not waver.

Verse Eight

The hand of the LORD will intervene when necessary to chastise and discipline. The Sefirah Gevurah brings justice to the world. Thus it can be said that the hand of the LORD is the action of Gevurah.

The Sefirah Gevurah will find your enemies. Your right hand will overtake all who hate You.

Verse Nine

Malachi 3:19 portrays the future as a glowing oven in which the wicked will be destroyed. The wicked have helped prepare the righteous for the day of the final Tikkun. The LORD will cleanse the world of the wicked, leaving the righteous. The righteous are easy to find because the wicked stand out because of their sins.

You will make the wicked as a fiery oven at the Tikkun. The LORD will let them perish in His anger, and the fire of the oven will devour them.

Verse Ten

The LORD will not allow the children of the wicked to be born. Their descendants will pay for the deeds of the wicked.

You will cause their fruit to vanish from the earth and their seed from among the children of men.

Verse Eleven

כִּי־נָטוּ עֲלֶיךָ (kee – nato alecha) – means “intended evil against.” This phrase expresses the intention to cause an inevitable fate to overtake another person. Wicked people plan to do evil against the LORD. The LORD will not allow the plan to come to be.

For they intended evil against You; they devised a plan, but they will fail.

Verse Twelve

For you will make them turn their backs; you will aim your bowstrings at their faces.

Verse Thirteen

It must be remembered that it is the LORD's omnipotence that we can recognize.

You are invincible, LORD, as seen through Your strength. We will proclaim You in song and sing of it.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirot Netzach, a psalm of David.

O LORD, in your strength, the King rejoices, and from your salvation, the power of Netzach he exults.

You have given him everything that he yearned for and gave him what his lips spoke. Meditate on this verse.

You made him the King of Israel and gave him good fortune.

He asked for life, and you gave it to him; a length of days and a future destiny.

The Sefirot Hod bestowed splendor and majesty upon him through Your salvation.

For You appointed him for blessings for the distant future; You made him shine with gladness in the LORD's sovereignty.

The King trusts in the LORD, and because of the blessings from the Sefirah Chesed, he will not waver.

The Sefirah Gevruah will find your enemies. Your right hand will overtake

You will make the wicked as a fiery oven at the Tikkun. The LORD will let them perish in His anger, and the fire of the oven will devour them.

You will cause their fruit to vanish from the earth and their seed from among the children of men.

For they intended evil against You; they devised a plan, but they will fail.

For you will make them turn their backs; you will aim your bowstrings at their faces.

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Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

